

IMPROVEMENT OF TEACHING THE TOPIC “BEGINNING TO WORK WITH ELECTRONIC MAIL” BASED ON SOFTWARE TOOLS

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Abstract

This article discusses the issues of creating multimedia presentations based on modern software tools and organizing lessons using them in teaching the topic “Getting Started with Email” in the 5th grade of “Informatics and Information Technologies” subject in general secondary schools today.

Keywords: Informatics and Information Technologies, Getting Started with Email, software tool, electronic manual, hypertext, sound, graphics, video, test, multimedia, animation, simulation model, general secondary education, software tool.

Introduction. The use of modern information technologies in education is certainly effective. Some opinions are critical of the impact of modern information technologies on the minds of young people, which is explained by the fact that young people are naturally attracted to the Internet and mobile communication devices. We all know that the problem cannot be solved by restricting mobile technology and the Internet, but young people still remain under criticism. Nowadays, when raising a well-rounded generation, it is necessary to teach the culture of using information on the Internet (information immunity). Directing interest in these technologies to the right goal is associated with increasing the national database. In particular, the increase in the national database in electronic applications and virtual educational systems in the education system serves as an effective tool for young people to learn.

It is known that about 25% of students can master the usual - traditional passage of the lesson, it has been proven by pedagogical scientists. Experience shows that simultaneously listening to the lecture, viewing the material on the computer screen and actively controlling its output on the screen increases the quality of mastering.

Pedagogical software is a didactic tool designed to partially or completely automate the educational process using computer technologies. They are promising for increasing the efficiency of the educational process. In the teaching of the subject "Informatics and Information Technologies" is considered one of the forms of using pedagogical software tools and is used as a means of teaching modern technologies. Pedagogical software tools include: a software product (a set of programs) aimed at achieving specific didactic goals in the subject, technical and methodological support, additional and auxiliary tools. When developing pedagogical software tools, the intellectual level, motivation, functional state and level of work of the students of the corresponding audience should be taken into account. The concept of motivation means the process of the individual acquiring significance for the activity being carried out, creating a stable interest in it, and transforming externally defined goals into internal needs. Thus, motivation can be recognized as an internal driving force that ensures the active

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involvement of a person in the educational process. It should be noted that the motivational qualities of a person form the basis of cognitive activity, in this process the student sets appropriate educational goals, manages the process and evaluates the level of its success. In this case, the need leads to the development of different levels of motivation for the student's professional formation in the process of independent learning. In the process of the student's professional formation, the following three levels of motivation can be distinguished: The initial level of motivation is associated with the need for professional development and arises on the basis of external social and personal motivations. The average level of motivation arises in the process of acquiring professional knowledge and creates the necessary foundations for further professional activity. A high level of motivation reflects the student's needs for development and the realization of his creative potential. The development of creative potential leads to the creation of optimal conditions for satisfying the student's needs for self-development.

In the study, we will consider improving the teaching of the topic "Starting Programming" using software tools, unlike the school textbook, to make it easier for teachers and students to learn, with animated actions.

The next topic given in the 5th grade "Informatics and Information Technologies" textbook of general secondary schools is the topic "Starting to Work with Email", and the following texts and images are given in the school textbook:

In this module, you will develop your skills in working with email to develop your project. In this project, you will work with your friends to write messages that are written and sent via email.

In addition, you will learn the following:

- how to send one email to several people;
- how to reply to emails;
- how to format text in emails (for example, change font type, size, and color);
- how to organize emails into folders;
- how to stay safe when using email.

Before you start You need to know the following:

- what email is and how to use it (you may not have used it yet);
- that you need to have an email account;
- how to log in to an email account;
- how to control the cursor and use the mouse buttons on a computer;

Introduction Email is email.

You need an email account to send and receive emails.

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You can get an email address from different email providers. For example, you can use Gmail or Microsoft Outlook. In this module, you will learn how to use Gmail. All providers have almost the same tools, but the buttons may be located in different parts.

When you have an email account, you also get an email address. In general, no two email addresses are the same. That is, each person's email address is unique. If two people had the same email address, they would receive your emails and you would receive their emails (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Email Work Window

If the email address you selected already exists, you will need to change the first part (in red). For example, you can add meaningful numbers at the end. For example, your favorite number.

When you click the transfer button in the window above, the following Email Work Window will open on the screen, which also contains the relevant buttons (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Email window

In addition to the information provided in the 5th grade "Informatics and Information Technologies" textbook, the study also presents animations on topics of interest to students based on software tools that they can understand and repeat over and over again.

After studying the topics given above, they can complete test tasks on the topics to consolidate their knowledge (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Test work window

Before working on the tests in the given window, the test selection window opens and in this window there is a sequence of topics, from which students can choose the one they like.

Similarly, the elements of the remaining sections and topics in the subject "Informatics and Information Technologies" of general secondary schools for the 5th grade, as well as the process of solving the relevant problems and the tasks to be performed are illustrated one by one in the multimedia electronic manual using animated developments.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of a multimedia electronic manual in teaching all topics of the subject "Informatics and Information Technologies" of general secondary schools for the 5th grade not only increases the efficiency of students' mastery, but also increases their opportunities for independent work.

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